

Sensory Lexicon Development for Alasa (African Star Apple – *Chrysophyllum albidum*)

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Executive Summary

This report presents the development of a standardized sensory lexicon for Alasa (African Star Apple – *Chrysophyllum albidum*), an indigenous fruit widely consumed in Ghana but understudied from a sensory science perspective. A structured multi-step approach—term generation, consensus building, reference anchoring, and Check-All-That-Apply (CATA) evaluation—was used to identify, refine, and validate descriptors across appearance, aroma, flavour, texture-in-hand, mouthfeel, and aftertaste. A total of 80 evaluations were conducted by eight trained panellists.

The final lexicon comprises 56 high-frequency descriptors representing the multisensory complexity of Alasa. These terms provide a standardized vocabulary for future sensory research, product development, quality control, and branding efforts related to indigenous fruits in Ghana.

Introduction

Many indigenous fruits in Ghana are valued for their flavour, cultural relevance, and nutritional contributions (Stadlmayr et al., 2013). Despite their importance, most have not been scientifically examined using structured sensory evaluation techniques. Alasa (African Star Apple), although widely consumed, lacks documented sensory characterization.

Purpose of Lexicon Development

The goal of this sensory lexicon development was to obtain a reliable, comprehensive, and culturally relevant set of descriptors for evaluating Alasa. The final lexicon will support sensory evaluation, quality control, product development, and marketing strategies for Alasa-derived or Alasa-inspired products.

Methodology

A structured lexicon development procedure was followed, consisting of:

1. Environmental control and standardized assessment setup
2. Panel selection, screening, and training
3. Sample sourcing, preparation, and presentation
4. Descriptive term generation
5. Consensus workshops and reference development
6. Lexicon validation through Check-All-That-Apply (CATA)
7. Descriptor retention based on $\geq 40\%$ frequency threshold

Environmental Controls

All assessments were conducted at the University of Ghana Sensory Evaluation Laboratory. The lab is purpose-built with tasting booths, white LED lighting, air-conditioning ($27 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$), and an extractor fan to minimize odours. Samples were served through hatches to limit interaction and ensure unbiased assessments. **Panel**

Selection and Training

Eight trained panellists were recruited based on their ability to identify basic tastes, recognise common odours, differentiate among sensory stimuli, and describe food products. Screening procedures involved ranking tests, odour recognition tasks, and difference tests, for panelist qualification. The panelists received further training in sensory modalities (appearance, aroma, flavour, texture-in-hand, mouthfeel, aftertaste) and participated in calibration sessions using reference standards.

Sample details

Fresh Alasa fruits were sourced from multiple locations across the Greater Accra Region to capture natural variation in maturity, colour, texture, and flavour. Ten samples were included in total.

Locations included:

- East Legon Melcom
- University of Ghana (Crop Science Department)
- University of Ghana (Law School)
- Ashongman Estate

Each sample included multiple ripening stages.

Table 1: Details of Star Fruit Samples Used

Location	Number of Ripening Levels	Date Harvested	Date Bought	Date Assessed
East Legon Melcom	3	-	16/04/2024	16/04/2024
UG Crop Science	4	30/04/2024	-	30/04/2024
UG Law School	5	30/04/2024	-	30/04/2024
Ashongman Estate	3	04/06/2024	-	06/06/2024

Madina

Nima Islamic Institute (Togo)

Adenta Lotto Kiosk (Volta)

Night market

St. John's Dome

Adenta Market

Adenta Market Roadside

Madina 2

Ashaiman Underbridge market (Ada 1)

Ashaiman Underbridge market

Ashaiman Underbridge market (Ada 2)

Ashaiman Market (Aburi)

Ashaiman Underbridge market (Nsawam)

Ashaiman Underbridge market (Aburi)

Adenta Station

Nima market (Nkawkaw)

Fig 1: Photos of the alasa samples used in the study

Sample Preparation and Presentation

Each fruit sample was washed, dried, and cut into uniform quarters. Samples were served in 40 cc lidded plastic cups, one quarter per assessor. Samples were coded and presented in randomized monadic form to avoid order bias.

Descriptor Generation and Consensus

Each assessor independently generated descriptive terms for all modalities. Terms were then consolidated during consensus meetings. Definitions, references, and anchors were developed to standardize interpretation. References included fresh fruits, brewed tea, sucrose solution, citric acid, and caffeine across modalities.

CATA-Based Lexicon Expansion

The consensus descriptors were compiled into a CATA checklist. Each assessor evaluated all 10 samples across the lexicon. In total, 80 evaluations (8 assessors × 10 samples) were recorded.

Descriptors selected in $\geq 40\%$ of evaluations (≥ 32 out of 80) were retained in the final lexicon.

Results and Discussion

The final sensory lexicon includes 56 descriptors across the six modalities. Below is the full set of attributes, definitions, references, and anchors retained.

Table 1. Final Sensory Lexicon for Alasa Fruit Based on $\geq 40\%$ Frequency Threshold (n = 80 evaluations)

Sensory Modality	Descriptor	Frequency (out of 80)
Appearance - Outer Skin	Firm	74
	Orange colour	54
	Black spots	49
	Yellow colour	40
	Red spots	40
Appearance - Flesh	Cream colour	75
	Whitish fluid	76
	Seed visible	77
	Firm	73
	Juicy	74
	Fibrous	76
	Reddish-brown colour	41
	Red-orange colour	47
	Orange colour	59
Appearance - Seed	Dark brown	77
	Cream layer	77
	Smooth	77
	Hard	75

	Glossy	76
	Oval shape	71
Aroma	Alasa-like	72
	Guava	46
	Sweet smell	63
Flavour - Skin	Bitter	69
Flavour - Inner Flesh	Alasa-like	73
	Sweet	50
	Sour	65
	Bitter	38
Flavour - Seed Area	Bitter	29 (<i>excluded</i>)***
Texture-in-hand - Skin	Firm	73
	Smooth	72
Texture-in-hand - Flesh	Moist	76
	Sticky	70
	Firm	71
Texture-in-hand - Seed	Hard	71
	Smooth	77
Mouthfeel - Skin	Rough	55
	Chewy	75
	Cohesive	64
Mouthfeel - Flesh	Chewy	70
	Adhesive	66
	Juicy	78
	Puckering	68
	Soft	76

	Cohesive	69
	Smooth	77
	Astringent	46
	Gum-like	60
Mouthfeel – Seed	Rubbery	70
	Smooth	75
	Hard	68
Aftertaste	Residue	67
	Astringent	55
	Sour	60
	Coating	75
	Bitter	36
	Sweet	36

Appearance Attributes

The visual attributes of the outer skin, flesh, and seed were among the most frequently selected descriptors. Key terms included *firm* (74), *orange colour* (54), *black spots* (49), and *red spots* (40), reflecting the natural variation of Alasa's skin. The flesh was characterised by descriptors such as *cream colour* (75), *whitish fluid* (76), *fibrous* (76), and *juicy* (74), highlighting the textural richness and freshness of the fruit. Seed attributes such as *dark brown*, *smooth*, and *oval shape* were consistently selected, indicating easy recognition.

Aroma Profile

The aroma of Alasa was captured by three key terms: *Alasa-like* (72), *sweet smell* (63), and *guava* (46). The frequent mention of "Alasa-like" suggests that the fruit possesses a unique and recognizable indigenous scent that is not easily replaced by other fruits. The reference to "guava" may reflect shared tropical volatiles or fermentation-related esters.

Flavour Characteristics

Flavour descriptors showed differentiation between fruit components. The skin was described predominantly as *bitter* (69). The inner flesh had a balanced profile of *Alasa-like* (73), *sour* (65), and *sweet* (50). Flavour descriptors for the seed area were excluded due to low frequency.

Texture-in-Hand and Mouthfeel

Texture-in-hand descriptors revealed the fruit's tactile complexity, particularly for the flesh (*moist*, *sticky*, *firm*) and the seed (*smooth*, *hard*). In-mouth sensations were robust, with terms like *chewy* (75), *juicy* (78), *cohesive* (69), and *astringent* (46) highlighting the fruit's unique sensory experience. Notably, descriptors such as *gum-like* (60) and *puckering* (68) possibly reflect the mucilaginous or tannin-like qualities of Alasa. The

seed's mouthfeel was characterized as **rubbery**, **smooth**, and **hard**, consistent with its visual and tactile features.

Aftertaste Attributes

The aftertaste profile was marked by *coating* (75), *residue* (67), and *sour* (60), indicating lingering sensations post-consumption.

CONCLUSION

The sensory lexicon development process for *Chrysophyllum albidum* (Alasa) successfully identified a comprehensive set of descriptors reflecting consumer perception of the fruit's appearance, aroma, texture, mouthfeel, and aftertaste. Out of the total descriptors generated, over 50 showed a frequency equal to or exceeding the 40% threshold, indicating their relevance and consistency across assessors. Key descriptors such as **“Juicy,” “Hard Seed,” “Smooth Seed,” “Whitish Fluid,” “Cream Layer,” and “Astringent”** emerged as dominant attributes, reflecting the fruit’s multisensory complexity. This lexicon provides a standardized vocabulary for future sensory studies, product development, and quality control of Alasa-based food products. Moreover, it lays the foundation for building a sensory profile or consumer panel assessment tailored to the cultural familiarity and unique sensory characteristics of indigenous fruits in West Africa.

References

- Stadlmayr, B., Charrondiere, U. R., Eisenwagen, S., Jamnadass, R., & Kehlenbeck, K. (2013). Nutrient composition of selected indigenous fruits from sub-Saharan Africa. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*, 93(11), 2627-2636.
- Suwonsichon, S. (2019). The importance of sensory lexicons for research and development of food products. *Foods*, 8(1), 27.

APPENDIX:

Table 1: Alasa, Attribute names, definitions, references and anchors developed across all modalities.

Modality	Descriptor	Definition	Anchor	References
Appearance <i>(Outer skin)</i>	Yellow colour	Intensity of yellow colour	Light - Dark	
	Yellow colour	Presence of yellow colour	Not - Very	
	Orange colour	Presence of orange colour	Not - very	
	Orange colour	Intensity of orange colour	Light - Dark	
	Black spots	Presence of black spots on the outer surface of sample	Present/ Not Present	
	Red spots	Presence of red spots on the outer surface of sample	Present/ Not Present	
	Firm	Outer surface of sample appears to have a compact texture and cannot be easily squished	Not - very	Semi-ripped saloon mango
Appearance <i>(Flesh)</i>	Reddish-Brown colour	Presence of reddish-brown colour	Not -very	
	Reddish-Brown colour	Intensity of reddish-brown colour	Light - Dark	
	Yellow colour	Intensity of yellow colour	Light - Dark	
	Yellow colour	Presence of yellow colour	Not - Very	
	Orange colour	Presence of orange colour	Not - very	
	Orange colour	Intensity of orange colour	Light - Dark	
	Red-orange colour	Presence of red-orange colour	Not - very	

	Red- orange colour	Intensity of red-orange colour	Light - Dark	
	Cream	Presence of off-white colour with streaks of brown	Not -very	
	Whitish fluid	Sample secretes a whitish sticky fluid	Present/ Not Present	
	Seed	Presence of seeds in sample	Present/ Not Present	
	Firm	Inner part of sample appears to have a compact texture and cannot be easily squished	Not-Very	Ripe pawpaw
	Juicy	Sample gives the impression that it contains a lot of juice	Not - very	Ripe pawpaw
	Fibrous	Sample has the presence thread- like and stringy structures within its pulp	Not - very	Ripe local mango
Appearance (Seed)	Dark brown	Presence of dark brown colour	Light-Dark	
	Cream layer	Seed has a thin, soft creamy coating covering it	Present/ Not present	
	Smooth	Seed appears to have an even surface	Not - Very	Soursop seed/ Apple skin
	Hard	Seed has a solid, rigid outer surface	Not - Very	Soursop seed
	Glossy	Seed appears to have a shiny surface	Not-Very	Glossy Chocolate /

				Soursop seed
	Oval shape	Sample has an oval (crescent) shaped seed	Present/ Not Present	
Aroma	Alasa	Characteristic smell of Alasa	Not-very	
	Guava	Sample has a smell like that of unripe guava	Not-Very	Unripe guava
	Sweet smell	Sample gives the impression that it will taste sweet	Not-Very	
	Fermented note	Sample has a fermented note	Not - Very	Fermented Corn dough
Texture in hand (Skin)	Firm	Skin has a compact texture and cannot be easily squished	Soft - Firm	Orange
	Smooth	Skin has an even feel when touched with the fingers	Rough - Smooth	Orange
Texture in hand (Flesh)	Moist	Sample releases juice when touched or pressed with the fingers	Not - Very	Ripe pawpaw
	Sticky	Sample has a which liquid which feels sticky between the fingers	Not - Very	Neem tree gum
	Firm	Inner flesh has a compact texture and cannot be easily squished	Soft - Firm	Ripe pawpaw

Texture in hand <i>(Seed area)</i>	Hard	Sample feels rigid and not easily compressible	Soft - Hard	Soursop seed
	Smooth	Sample feels even when touched with the fingers	Rough - Smooth	Soursop seed
Flavour <i>(Skin)</i>	Bitter	Basic taste bitter	Not - Very	Caffeine
Flavour <i>(Inner flesh)</i>	Alasa	Characteristic taste of alasa	Not - Very	
	Sweet	Basic taste sweet	Not - Very	Sucrose
	Sour	Basic taste sour	Not - Very	Citric acid
	Bitter	Basic taste bitter	Not - Very	Caffeine
Flavour <i>(Seed area)</i>	Bitter	Basic taste bitter	Not - Very	Caffeine
Mouthfeel <i>(Outer skin)</i>	Rough	Sample has an even feel in the mouth	Smooth - Rough	Semi ripened saloon mango peel
	Chewy	Sample needs to be chewed a while before swallowing	Not - Very	Unripe pawpaw
	Cohesive	Ability of particles to stick together when chewed with the molars.	Not - Very	Soursop pulp
Mouthfeel <i>(Inner flesh)</i>	Chewy	Duration it takes sample to be completely broken down before swallowing	Not - Very	Ripe pawpaw pulp

	Adhesive	Sample sticks to the palette when chewed in the mouth	Not - Very	Gummy bear
	Juicy	Sample releases an amount of juice when chewed	Not-Very	Ripe saloon mango
	Puckering	Stinging discomfort in the jaws or side of the mouth	Not-Very	Lemon
	Soft	Ease to bite through sample with incisors	Not-Very	Ripe saloon mango
	Cohesive	Ability of particles to stick together when chewed with the molars.	Not-Very	Chewing Gum
	Smooth	Sample has an even feel while chewed in the mouth	Not-Very	Soursop pulp
	Astringent	Dryness in the mouth	Not-Very	Brewed black tea
	Gum	Inner part turns into gum after chewing for about 2 minutes	Present/ Not present	Chewing gum
Mouthfeel (Seed area)	Rubbery	Presence of rubbery coating on seeds	Not-Very	
	Smooth	Sample has an even feel in the mouth	Rough - Smooth	Soursop seed
	Hard	Sample feels rigid and cannot easily be compressed	Soft - Hard	Soursop seed
Aftertaste	Residue	Presence of particles in the mouth after swallowing	Not-Very	

	Astringent	Sample leaves mouth dry after swallowing	Not-Very	Black tea
	Bitter	Basic taste bitter	Not-Very	Caffeine
	Sour	Lingering Basic taste sour	Not-Very	Citric acid
	Sweet	Basic taste sweet	Not - Very	Sucrose
	Coating	Sample leaves a sticky coating on the lips and teeth after swallowing	Not - Very	Neem tree gum